

**Acetylenic Derivatives from
*Moscharia pinnatifida***

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MOSCHARIA pinnatifida Ruiz. et Pav. is an annual herb and belongs to family Compositae, tribe Mutisieae and subtribe Nassauviinae¹. Previous studies on this plant led to the isolation of tridecapentaynene from the roots² and of α -isocedrene, cyperene, guaiane and nerolidol derivatives from the aerial parts³. We have recently reported a new guaiane ester from its aerial parts⁴. The present paper describes the isolation and identification of acetylenic spiroketals (1-3) from the aerial parts.

Experimental

The air-dried and coarsely powdered aerial parts (1 kg) of the plant was extracted with MeOH-Et₂O-petrol (1 : 1 : 1) mixture at room temperature; extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure. The concentrated extract was defatted by putting overnight in a refrigerator in MeOH. The defatted extract on column chromatography over silica gel (PF 254) gave five fractions, viz. 1 (petrol), 2 (Et₂O-

petrol, 4 : 1), 3 (Et₂O-petrol, 1 : 1), 4 (Et₂O) and 5 (Et₂O-MeOH, 9 : 1). Uv spectral measurements of fractions 2 and 3 showed the presence of acetylenic moieties. Therefore these two fractions were taken for further investigation. Fraction 2 was separated by prep-*tlc* in CH₂Cl₂-C₆H₆ (1 : 1) and afforded spiroketal (1) (25 mg) alongwith squalene (60 mg), phytol ester (50 mg), lupeol (800 mg) and taraxasterol (600 mg), while fraction 3 on prep-*tlc* in CH₂Cl₂-C₆H₆-Et₂O (4 : 4 : 1) gave spiroketals 2 (30 mg) and 3 (32 mg).

Results and Discussion

The molecular formulae of compounds 1-3 were deduced from accurate mass measurements of their molecular ion peaks. The presence of acetylenic moiety was ascertained by the appearance of ir bands at 2 140-2 150 cm⁻¹. The structures were finally elucidated from ¹H nmr (400 MHz) and NOE studies and their identity was further confirmed⁵.
Spiroketal 1 : colourless oil, *m/z* 214 [*M*⁺] for C₁₄H₁₄O₂ ; ν_{max} (CCl₄) 2 140 (C≡C) and 1 635 cm⁻¹ (C=C) ; δ (400 MHz ; CDCl₃) 2.01 (3H, d, *J* 1 Hz, H-14), 1.78-2.05 (6H, m, H-2, H-3, H-4), 3.84 (1H, m, H-1'), 4.11 (1H, ddd, H-1), 4.61 (1H, s br, H-9), 6.17 (1H, dd, *J* 5, 1 Hz, H-6) and 6.21 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, H-7) ;
Spiroketal 2 : colourless gum, *m/z* (rel. int.) 230.0942 [*M*⁺] (100) (Calcd. for C₁₄H₁₄O₃ : 230.0941), 199 [*M*-CH₂OH]⁺ (24), 156 (80) ; ν_{max} (CCl₄) 3 500 (OH), 2 140 (C≡C), 1 635, 1 580 (C=C), 1 100 (C-O-C), 1 030 cm⁻¹ (C-O) ; δ (400 MHz ; CDCl₃) 1.87 (1H, m, H-3'), 1.91 (2H, m, H-4, H-4'), 1.98 (3H, d, *J* 1 Hz, H-14), 2.08 (1H, m, H-3), 3.82 (1H, d br, *J* 6.5 Hz, H-1'), 3.85 (1H, m, H-2), 3.88 (1H, dd, *J* 6.5, 2 Hz, H-1), 5.00 (1H, s br, H-9), 6.19 (1H, dd, *J* 5, 2 Hz, H-6) and 6.68 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, H-7) ;
Spiroketal 3 : colourless oil, *m/z* (rel. int) 230.0942 [*M*⁺] (100) (calcd. for C₁₄H₁₄O₃ : 230.0941), 199 [*M*-CH₂OH]⁺ (22), 156 (80) ; ν_{max} (CCl₄) 3 500 (OH), 2 150 (C≡C), 1 635-1 580 (C=C), 1 100 and 1 030 cm⁻¹ ; δ (400 MHz ; CDCl₃) 1.87 (1H, m, H-3), 1.91 (2H, m, H-4, H-4'), 2.01 (3H, d, *J* 1 Hz, H-14), 2.08 (1H, m, H-3), 3.82 (1H, d br, *J* 6.5 Hz, H-1'), 3.85 (1H, m, H-2), 3.88 (1H, dd, *J* 6.5, 2 Hz, H-1), 4.65 (1H, s br, H-9), 6.15 (1H, d, *J* 5 Hz, H-6) and 6.24 (1H, *J* 5 Hz, H-7).

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